

Kinetics and Reaction Mechanism of Hydrolysis of *N*-Salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline

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The hydrolysis of Schiff bases is an important reaction of biochemical interest¹. Several workers²⁻⁴ have studied the catalytic effect of hydrogen ions, hydroxyl ions and metal ions on the hydrolysis of imines. We present here a systematic study of the hydrolysis mechanism of the imine, *N*-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline in the pH range 3.57–12.65.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants in the pH range 3.57–12.65 at 29° are given in Table 1. A rate profile diagram of pH vs rate constant (Fig. 1) at 29° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ shows that the rate is minimum at $7.95 < \text{pH} < 9.95$, and it is virtually constant at $\text{pH} > 10.76$.

Fig. 1. Plot of k against pH at 29° for the hydrolysis of *N*-salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline at $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

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Rate-limiting pathways : In the pH range 3.57–12.65, the Schiff base (HL) may be assumed to undergo hydrolysis by four rate-determining pathways² : (i) the acid-catalysed addition of water to the imine linkage of the protonated Schiff base, H_2L^+ (k_1), (ii) the spontaneous addition of water to the imine linkage of the neutral Schiff base, HL (k_2), (iii) the addition of water to the imine anion, L (k_3) and (iv) the addition of hydroxyl ion to the imine anion, L (k_4). The last step in which the hydroxyl ion predominates may be eliminated as the rate constant was found to be almost independent of the hydroxyl ion concentration at $\text{pH} > 10.76$ (Table 1). Thus the overall rate of hydrolysis will be

$$\text{Rate} = k_1(\text{H}_2\text{L}^+) + k_2(\text{HL}) + k_3(\text{L}) \quad (1)$$

The deprotonation and protonation equilibria of the imine (HL) may be represented as

Hydrolysis of Schiff base in acidic and neutral range of pH : The rate constant varies linearly with the hydrogen ion concentration in the pH range 4.36–7.04 (Table 1). In this pH range, equation (1) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] + k_2 [\text{HL}]$$

$$k = \frac{k_1}{K_1} [\text{H}^+] + k_2 \quad (2)$$

A plot of k vs $[\text{H}^+]$ was found to be a straight line with slope k_1/K_1 from which k_1 was calculated as $4.98 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 29°. Since the intercept of the plot was

TABLE 1 – RATE CONSTANT DATA FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-SALICYLIDENE-*p*-METHYLANILINEEthanol-water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 29°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

pH	$\times 10^7 [\text{H}^+]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^5 [\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^3 k$ s^{-1}
3.57	2 692.00	—	26.00
4.36	436.50	—	12.50
4.58	263.00	—	6.70
5.06	87.10	—	2.90
5.42	38.02	—	0.88
6.30	7.21	—	0.80
7.04	0.91	—	0.74
7.95	—	0.09	0.60
8.34	—	0.22	—
8.82	—	0.66	—
9.95	—	8.91	2.60
10.76	—	58.00	8.20
11.60	—	398.00	9.60
11.75	—	562.00	9.77
12.00	—	1 000.00	10.20
12.30	—	1 995.00	10.70
12.39	—	2 455.00	11.10
12.60	—	3 981.00	11.30
12.65	—	4 467.00	13.40

zero, k_2 was taken as zero. In the acidic pH range, the proton-catalysed attack of water on the reactive imine linkage of (HL) is suggested to be the rate-limiting step for the hydrolysis.

The reaction scheme has been presented in our previous communication³. The low rates in the neutral pH range are due to negligible protonation of the imine. Hence the attack of water on the protonated imine is slow. The addition of water to the neutral imine⁴ (HL) is therefore suggested to be the rate-limiting step. In the hydrolysis study, specific acid catalysis is assumed as no general catalysis was observed (Table 2).

Hydrolysis of Schiff base in basic medium: In the basic range (pH > 8.82), there is an initial increase in rate with increase in pH, and at pH > 10.76, the rate is nearly independent of the hydroxyl ion concentration (Table 1). In this pH range, the Schiff base may be assumed to be exclusively in the anionic form L^- ($pK_2 = 10.400$) due to the neutralisation of the phenolic pro-

ton of the *ortho*-hydroxyl group by the OH^- ion of alkali². These observations lead to the assumption that the complex formed may be 'Arrhenius complex'. In the presence of excess catalyst, 'Arrhenius complex' leads to 'specific hydroxyl ion catalysis' at low hydroxyl ion concentration and the rate reaches a limiting value at high hydroxyl ion concentration⁷. In the present study, it is observed that the rate increases with the hydroxyl ion concentration at low hydroxyl ion concentrations. Since no general catalysis was observed in this region (Table 2), specific hydroxyl ion catalysis may be assumed. Further, the rate reaches a limiting value at higher hydroxyl ion concentrations. All these facts indicate that the rate-limiting step is the slow reaction of the imine anion L^- with water (k_4)^{2,7}. The reaction scheme has been presented in our previous communication³. The average value of the rate constants at pH > 10.76 is taken as k_4 ($k_4 = 12.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 29°). The resulting carbinolamine then decomposes at a fast rate to give the products of hydrolysis.

Effect of temperature and thermodynamic parameters: From the effect of temperature on the rate of hydrolysis carried out in the range 29–45°, the different activation parameters like energy of activation (E), probability factor (PZ), ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* were evaluated. The ΔS^* values range from -64.40 to -257.33 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ in the pH range 3.57–12.65. The negative ΔS^* values obtained can perhaps be explained by a model in which the water molecules are tightly held to the reactive imine linkage, the nucleus of the hydrolytic reaction. The large negative ΔS^* values may indicate on extensive reorientation of the solvent molecules as a result of the formation of the activated complex.

Experimental

The imine was prepared by refluxing calculated amounts of salicylaldehyde and *p*-toluidine in ethanolic medium for ~ 1 h. On cooling, the resulting yellow coloured crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 99°. Its structure was confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra.

The rate of hydrolysis was followed spectrophotometrically at 421 nm by using an Elico CL-54 spec-

TABLE 2 - GENERAL ACID-BASE CATALYSIS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-SALICYLIDENE-*p*-METHYLANILINEEthanol-water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 29°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol. dm}^{-3}$

Potassium hydrogen phthalate (PHIP) and hydrochloric acid buffer (pH = 3.57) :

$([\text{PHIP}] + [\text{HCl}]) (\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3})$	2.25	4.50	6.75	9.00	11.25
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	26.05	28.80	31.77	28.38	26.91

Acetate buffer (pH = 4.58) :

$([\text{HA}] + [\text{A}^-]) (\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3})$	8.00	16.00	24.00	32.00	40.00
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	6.82	5.90	5.99	5.73	6.11

Phosphate buffer (pH = 7.04) :

$([\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-] + [\text{HPO}_4^{2-}]) (\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3})$	8.00	16.00	24.00	32.00	40.00
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	0.76	0.91	0.74	0.73	0.91

Carbonate buffer (pH = 10.76) :

$([\text{HCO}_3^-] + [\text{CO}_3^{2-}]) (\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3})$	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	7.00	7.77	7.94	8.15	8.37

trophotometer. Universal buffer solutions were prepared according to the reported methods⁸. The pH was determined using an Elico LI-120 pH meter. The concentration of the imine was kept at $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. A 1 M sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) was used to keep the ionic strength constant at $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. A.R. grade (E. Merck) chemicals were used throughout.

The plots of $\log (A_t - A_\infty)$ against time were found to be straight lines and the pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the slopes of these plots. From the effect of temperature on the rate, the various thermodynamic parameters were evaluated.

pK_1 was determined by potentiometric titration of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ Schiff base against 0.01 M HCl using a pH meter, equipped with a combined glass-calomel electrode assembly. pK_1 was found to be 4.731 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 29° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The Schiff base anion (L^-) showed λ_{max} at 421 nm. pK_2 was calculated spectrophotometrically as 10.400 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 29° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

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